

THE EMERGENCE AND ORIGINS OF UZBEK WRESTLING

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the sport of wrestling, the history of its formation, the origin and rules of Uzbek wrestling. The importance of wrestling for man and society was also revealed.

Keywords: kurash, national kurash, International Kurash Association, Pahlavon Mahmud, Sodiq Polvon, Belt Wrestling Federation of Uzbekistan, Komil Yusupov, rules of kurash.

INTRODUCTION

A society with increased attention to sports develops as a healthy society. There are all types of sports that serve not only physical fitness, but also spiritual development of a person. In particular, wrestling is a defense of national values, and it provides strengthening of feelings of national pride, pride and confidence in a bright future. The art of fighting has been known in many nations since ancient times. This sport is a one-on-one match between two athletes according to established rules. Wrestling was widespread in ancient times, especially in Greece, and took a permanent place in the ancient Olympic competitions. Today, various forms of national wrestling exist in Greece, Italy, Japan, Turkey, Iran, Afghanistan, Russia, Uzbekistan, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and other countries.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The basic rules of modern sports wrestling began to appear in several European countries in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. In 1912, the International Amateur Wrestling Federation (FILA) was established (now it has 144 member countries, in particular, our country became a member in 1993). Greco-Roman wrestling, freestyle wrestling, judo, sambo and other types of sports wrestling are widespread in the international arena.[1] In the following years, Uzbek wrestling began to be recognized on a world scale as a separate form of wrestling. Wrestling is one of the main means of training a person to be strong, dexterous, resilient and strong-willed. It is allowed to engage in wrestling from the age of 12 under the supervision of specialists. Archeological findings and historical manuscripts confirm that wrestling has been an integral part of Uzbek lifestyle since ancient times. Two wrestlers fight on a Bronze Age cylinder found in ancient Bactria. Another artefact shows wrestling techniques of wrestlers. These unique findings mean that wrestling was a part of our ancestors' way of life even before 1.5 thousand BC. According to the Greek writer Claudius Aelian (II-III century) and other historical figures, Saka girls chose their grooms by competing with young men. Later, the girls determined the bridegroom by setting a condition, and this condition consisted of a wrestling match. An example of this is the conditions of Barchin in the Uzbek folk heroic epic - "Alpomish". does... [2]". This definition is close to the rules of modern wrestling. Also, Mahmoud Koshghari's "Devonu Lug'otit Turk", Alisher Navoi's "Hamsa", "Holoti Pahlavon Muhammad", Zayniddin Vasifi's "Badoye' ul-Waqaye", Husayn Vaiz Koshifi's

"" "Futuvvatnomai Sultaniy", Z.M. Babur's work "Boburnoma" contains valuable information about the struggle. In the 9th-16th centuries, wrestling became popular among the people. During this period, Pahlavon Mahmud and Sadiq Polvan were known throughout the East.

There is also a type of Uzbek folk singles wrestling called belt wrestling. There are many finds and historical manuscripts related to this. A figurine found in Mesopotamia 5,000 years ago depicts wrestlers competing in belt wrestling. In the Chinese manuscript "Tan-shu" it is written that the Dovan state (Fergana valley) does not have weddings and elections without wrestling competitions. Ahmad Polvan and Khoja Polvan gained fame in this type of wrestling (end of the 19th - 20th centuries). At the beginning of the century) during Tsarism and the Shuras, on the basis of ideological movements, an attempt was made to artificially suppress the Uzbek national struggle from the people's way of life.

By the end of the 90s of the 20th century, these attempts were terminated.

In 1991, Kamil Yusupov, a representative of the dynasty of wrestlers and an international master of sports in several types of wrestling, developed the following rules of Uzbek wrestling adapted to international standards: The wrestlers are from 14 x 14 m to 16 x 16 m, the edge is red compete standing on a blue-green carpet marked with a colored "dangerous line". It is not recommended to use the method of feeding. 81, 90, 100 kg and more than 100 kg, women compete in 48, 52, 57, 63, 70, 78, and more than 78 kg weight categories (children, women, seniors). and in girls' competitions, weight categories are determined taking into account age characteristics).

DISCUSSION

In 1992, the kugash federation was established in Uzbekistan. The 2003 Congress of the International Wrestling Association (IKA) in Tashkent set the time limit of 3 minutes in official competitions in order to ensure that each match was intense. In accordance with the methods used, they are evaluated as "Chala", "Yonbosh", "Halal", and "Reprimand", "Dakki", "Ghin-om" punishments for actions that violate the rules. is given. If the wrestler gets a ""honest"" rating (or his opponent is punished with ""ghin-om""), it means his victory. Getting a "side" twice (or being punished by an opponent with two "dakki") also means victory. ""Chala" grades are taken into account... In the event of equality of points, the wrestler who received the last grade wins, if the number of grades and penalties of the wrestler are equal, the grade has priority, if the number of penalties is equal, the one who received the last penalty is the loser. , if there is a tie (or no score and penalty), the winner will be declared by majority vote of the referee[3].

In 2001, a belt wrestling federation was established in Uzbekistan[4]. In September 1998, in Tashkent, representatives of 28 countries (USA, Bolivia, Great Britain, Holland, Russia, Uzbekistan, Japan, etc.) became the founders of the International Wrestling Association (IKA), and in this connection, Uzbek wrestling took place here. a major international competition was held. The President's speech "in support of the International Kugash Association" ensured the further development of Uzbek national wrestling. This year in Tashkent

The first Uzbek Kugash World Championship, an international women's competition was held in Bryansk, Russia. The International Wrestling Academy was established under IKA.

In 2000, the wrestling month was held in Uzbekistan. During this month, about 2 million people went to the wrestling mat. A traditional international competition named after the honorary president of IKA Islam Karimov was founded in Great Britain. Since 2001, the International Wrestling Institute has been operating in Tashkent. 66 national federations

became members of IKA. European, Asian, Pan American and Oceanic wrestling confederations were formed. Currently, more than 600,000 people are engaged in Uzbek wrestling in foreign countries. World, continental and country championships in this type of wrestling, as well as many other international competitions dedicated to the memory of al-Tirmizi, Pahlavon Mahmud and many others are regularly held in Uzbekistan. The Olympic Council of Asia included this type of wrestling in the program of the Asian Games in 2003. Bahrom Anazov, Isoq Akhmedov, Makhtumkuli Mahmudov, Kamal Murodov, Toshtemir Muhammadiyev, Akobir Kurbanov (Uzbekistan), Kubashkhanim Elknur, Selim Totar oghly (Turkey), Alexander Katsuragi will participate in the world wrestling championships. , Carlos Honorato (Brazil), Pawel Melananetz (Poland), Hiroyoshi Kashimoto (Japan) and others won and received prizes.

RESULTS

Wrestling, one of the traditional sports of the Uzbek people, has a history of three and a half thousand years. Wrestling is an Uzbek word, and it is mentioned in a number of ancient Eastern literary sources as a one-on-one combat and social entertainment sport.

In the legendary Alpomish epic with a thousand-year history, it is explained that in the distant past, wrestling was the most popular and popular sport on the land of Uzbekistan.

A number of philosophers and historians who lived and worked in ancient and medieval times mentioned the struggle with special respect in their works.

Ibn Sina admitted that wrestling is the best way to ensure health of soul and body. However, there is still no clear information about when and where the fight started. In turn, such abstraction could not be an obstacle for recognition of wrestling as one of the ancient sports by a number of scientists. In the 9th century, the development of wrestling reached a new level. At that time, the population living in the territory of modern Uzbekistan was traditional during festivals, weddings, and large public events, wrestling was used as a means of entertainment and recreation. Later, wrestling became an independent sport and a method of physical training from a means of entertainment. The strongest wrestlers became famous among the people, and legends began to be woven about them. Pahlavon Mahmud, who lived in the 12th century, is a clear example of this. His grave is still a favorite place of pilgrims and one of the holy places.

Amir Temur, an incomparable general and statesman who left a bright mark in human history in the 14th century, used wrestling to train his soldiers and improve their physical fitness. It is known that Amir Temur's army was considered the most powerful and invincible army of his time.

Over time, wrestling has become one of the most beloved and honored traditions of the population living in the territory of modern Uzbekistan. In this sense, it is no exaggeration to say that the struggle is ingrained in the blood of Uzbeks. Love for this sport is inherited from fathers to children. To date, the number of regular wrestlers in Uzbekistan alone has exceeded two million. The number of fans and amateurs of this sport is countless.

In the early 1980s, the famous Uzbek wrestling master, judo fighter and sambo fighter Kamil Yusupov started researching the rich heritage of Uzbek wrestling. The main goal of this person was to develop new rules of fighting that correspond to international standards. By the beginning of the nineties, successfully fulfilling this honorable task, he set himself the goal of bringing Uzbek wrestling to the international arena. At first, he introduced the wrestling rules he had developed to the public, experts, and fans.

The new rules incorporate the most honored traditions of Uzbek wrestling and international sports standards such as special uniforms, the place of competition and the duration of the competition. Sports experts have recognized that the wrestling rules developed by Komil Yusupov fully meet the requirements of international sports. One of the main advantages of wrestling rules is that they do not allow the contest to continue while lying down. As soon as the knee of one of the athletes touches the mat, the referee stops the competition and the wrestlers continue the competition while standing. This ensures that the fight is fast-paced and fun and exciting for the fans. In addition, the rules of wrestling prohibit the use of techniques that catch the lower part from the belt or cause pain and strangulation. In this way, wrestling has become one of the safest sports in which injuries to athletes are prevented [5].

Independence of Uzbekistan in 1991 gave new life to the struggle. The revival of wrestling, which is considered a national sport, was defined as one of the priorities of the state policy. The main goal is to turn wrestling into a real international sport, and then to include it in the program of the Olympic Games.

The efforts of struggle activists were not limited to Uzbekistan. Since 1992, they have participated in various prestigious sports conferences held in South Korea, Canada, Japan, India, the USA, Monaco and Russia, aimed at promoting Uzbek wrestling. On November 4, 2020, on the basis of the decision PQ-4881 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the national sport of wrestling and further increase its international prestige", "The national sport of wrestling will be brought to a new stage by 2025 Concept of withdrawal" was developed. In it, the problems that hinder the popularization and development of the national sport of wrestling and the tasks of their elimination were determined. At the same time, the priorities of increasing the prestige of Uzbekistan in the world by making wrestling one of the favorite sports of the peoples of the world and widely promoting its humanitarian ideas were determined.

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